

hatchability 81%. Males lived 27 days and females 33 days, and fecundity was 513 eggs. Data are equivalent to BPH biotype 1 data from TN1 plants.

Leersia-reared BPH fed little on rice plants, as indicated by low amounts of excreta, and did not survive on TN1 and several resistant varieties. Rice-plant-reared BPH populations, tested in the greenhouse, did not live on *Leersia*, but could contribute to the rice-feeding BPH gene pool through intermingling.

A crossing experiment was conducted to determine if *Leersia*-reared and rice-plant-reared BPH mate and to assess the virulence of the offspring. Individual fifth-instar nymphs of *Leersia*-reared BPH were placed in test tubes containing *Leersia* cuttings and greenhouse rice-reared BPH were placed in test tubes containing TN1 seedlings. Using adults that emerged simultaneously, crosses of

Survival of progeny from crosses between *Leersia* brown planthopper (BPH) and rice-reared BPH at 15 days after being placed on *Leersia* and TN1 plants.

Leersia BPH and rice-reared BPH were caged on *Leersia* and TN1 plants planted together in a clay pot. When eggs hatched, 10 newly emerged nymphs were caged on separate potted *Leersia* and TN1 plants. Some F₁ progenies sur-

vived (see figure) and produced F₂ progenies on *Leersia* and TN1 plants. If intermingling also occurs under field conditions, the wild *Leersia* BPH population can contribute to BPH field infestation. ♪

The flea beetle as a rice pest in Assam, India

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The flea beetle *Chaetonema basalis* Baly. was studied on rice plants during transplanting and tillering stages in ahu (March-July) and sali (July-December)

1980-81 in Assam, India. Mild infestations were reported in Barpeta Agricultural Subdivision, Kamrup, Assam, but there was no significant economic damage.

Adults are small, round, black, shining beetles about 1.5 to 2 mm long. They are found on leaves and jump when disturbed. They feed by scraping the green matter from leaves, leaving short straight lines on the leaf surface

that are parallel to leaf veins. Damage resembles that caused by the rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera*. Later, ends of affected leaves turn brown and wither. Heavily infested fields look scorched. In severely infested fields 25-40 beetles/hill can be found.

A rabi oilseed survey has shown that the pest also attacks mustard pods during winter. ♪

Rice thrips in Mymensingh, Bangladesh

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Rice thrips *thrips oryzae* Williams have become a major problem at the INA experimental farm, Mymensingh, and in adjacent areas. During 1982 aus season (summer rice) all varieties on the farm (high yielding and local) were severely damaged. In some cases infestation was 100%.

Infestation occurs in seedling and early growth stages. Thrips nymphs and adults suck sap from the leaves. In heavy infestation plants may dry.

Thrips increase might have been

caused by the long winter and summer drought and by the destruction of natural enemies through heavy insecticide application. Infestation decreased with the onset of rainy season. ♪

Status of the brown planthopper in Thailand

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Brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is one of the most destruc-

tive rice pests in central Thailand. In 1981, 36,000 ha were severely damaged. In a survey of pest status April-June 1981, BPH populations and natural enemies were estimated by direct counting (50 hills/field) and sweep net (50 sweeps/field) at 42 sites in 9 provinces, BPH eggs and egg parasites were sampled by dissecting 10 random hills at each location. BPH was in 95% of samples. Density was 204 adults and nymphs/50 hills and 6.5/50 sweeps (see table). Rice ragged stunt disease (RSV) was in 43% of sites, averaging 5% infected hills. Natural enemies — damselflies, wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, long-jawed orb weaver *Tetragnatha* spp, and coccinellid beetle *Micrapis discolor* — were abundant. Mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* population was

Population densities of brown planthopper (BPH) and its predators, and ragged stunt disease (RSV) incidence in central Thailand, April-June 1981.

Species	Sampling method	No. ^a	Occurrence in sampling areas (%)
BPH <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	Direct count	204.3	95.2
	Sweep net	6.5	75.7
BPH eggs	Stem dissection	61.4	78.8
Damselflies	Sweep net	23.2	100.0
<i>Lycosa pseudoannulata</i>	Direct count	7.8	97.6
	Sweep net	2.1	37.8
<i>Tetragnatha</i> spp.	Sweep net	14.8	83.8
<i>Micrapis discolor</i>	Sweep net	11.6	78.4
<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	Sweep net	4.8	40.5
RSV	Direct count	5.2(%) ^b	42.9

^aNumber/50 hills or 50 sweeps except eggs, which were taken from 10 hills. ^b% infected hills of 50 hills.

low, 4.8/50 sweeps at 41% of the sites. There were 61.4 BPH eggs/ 10 hills in dissected stems, but an average 61% of eggs were parasitized, mostly by *Anagrus* sp. and *Oligosita* sp.

Sixty-six percent of fields sampled

had transplanted rice. The remainder had direct, wet-seeded. RD1, RD7, and RD11 predominated. High rates of nitrogenous fertilizers, ranging from 24 to 89 kg N/ha (av 46 kg N/ha) were applied. Most farmers used a 16-20-0 fertil-

izer formulation. Two or three insecticide applications per growing season were made to 94% fields sampled. Carbofuran, monocrotophos, and carbaryl were the most common insecticides. Application rates were lower than recommended dosages — 10-20 g or ml/ 20 liters water for spray formulation, and 0.5 kg ai/ ha for granular formulation.

Results indicated outbreaks of BPH and RSV are probably caused by cultivation practices. Farmers grow susceptible high tillering varieties, apply high fertilizer rates, and practice double or continuous cropping. Insecticides may not be critical to insect outbreaks. Damage by BPH and RSV will increase because of high insect density and disease reservoirs unless farmers adopt new insect-resistant varieties and modern pest management practices. *h*

Predatory potential of the wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* on rice brown planthopper

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Several species of spiders in rice ecosystems prey on and effectively regulate rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. The wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata* is the predominant species in irrigated wetland rice at Coimbatore, India. To determine the predatory potential of wolf spider on

brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, glasshouse studies were made at Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore.

In the first experiment, 20 5th-instar BPH nymphs were placed on potted rice plants as food for each spider. In the second experiment, 20 adult BPH (10 brachypterous and 10 macropterous forms) were used. Fourth-instar spiders were used in both experiments and all the spiders molted at least once during the 15-day experimental period. Ten replications (hills) were maintained in

each experiment.

The number of BPH eaten or killed by each spider was recorded daily. A constant population of live BPH in the same stage was maintained. The same spiders were used throughout the experiment.

Each spider consumed an average of 6 5th-instar BPH nymphs/day. When brachypterous and macropterous adults at 1:1 were provided as food, each spider consumed 7 adults/day. Spiders did not prefer one form to the other. *h*

Life history of rice bug *Leptocoris oratorius* (F.)

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The life history of the rice bug *Leptocoris oratorius* (F.) was studied in the greenhouse at 27.4° C (range 20.5-34.3° C) and relative humidity of 81% (range 63.0-93.8%).

Newly laid eggs from an adult colony maintained on potted plants were clipped from leaves and placed on moist filter paper in a petri dish for incubation. Emerging nymphs were transferred in pairs to milk-stage panicles of potted

1. Mylar film cage measures 7.5 cm in diameter, 30 cm long. Nylon mesh sleeves at the ends are 13 cm long.